

NOTES

TABLE—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES AND OTHER CHARACTERISING DATA.

Complex	Elemental Analyses%				Colour	Magnetic moment B.M.	Λ_M $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{mole}^{-1}$	Removal of water or tetrahydrofuran (% loss at temperature)		
	C	H	N	Cl				1H ₂ O	2H ₂ O	1 THF
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1. [(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂)Cl ₂ Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ bis(4-OH Benz)en Ti(III)]Cl	(41.90) 42.22	(6.16) 5.99	(6.63) 5.98	(18.65) 18.91	yellow	1.75	*	—	—	—
2. [(C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂)Cl ₂ Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ bis(4-OH Benz) o-phen Ti(III)]Cl	(51.46) 51.14	(3.40) 3.44	(5.95) 5.86	(34.93) 33.90	dirty white	1.44	68.8	—	—	—
3. [(C ₂₈ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₅)Cl ₂ Ti]Cl H ₂ O [Cl ₂ 2H ₂ O.bis(4-OH Benz)dian. Ti(III)]Cl.H ₂ O	(53.40) 53.52	(5.30) 5.53	(4.23) 4.39	(26.74) 26.56	yellow	*	22.7	68°C (2.54)	128°C (8.61) 8.51	—
4. [(C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃)Cl ₂ Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ 2H ₂ O.bis(4-OH Benz)Bn. Ti(III)]Cl	(48.45) 47.92	(4.78) 5.21	(4.82) 4.91	(16.10) 16.21	light yellow	1.48	29.7	—	180°C (5.99) 5.28	—
5. [(C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₂ OCl ₁)Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ bis(4-Cl-Benz)Bn.THF. Ti(III)]Cl	(55.43) 55.08	(3.56) 4.63	(4.52) 4.58	(28.59) 27.40	dirty white	*	70.3	—	—	228°C (14.90) 14.30
6. [(C ₂₈ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₃ .Cl ₄)Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ 2H ₂ O.bis(4-Cl Benz)dian. Ti(III)]Cl	(48.01) 48.03	(3.83) 4.01	(4.11) 4.08	(26.81) 26.04	brown	1.52	68.8	—	150°C (5.88) 6.00	—
7. [(C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₁)Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ bis(4-Cl-Benz)o-phen Ti(III)]Cl	(49.41) 50.02	(3.16) 3.86	(5.52) 5.49	(25.12) 24.90	dirty white	1.47	69.9	—	—	—
8. [(C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ Cl ₂)Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ bis(2-MeO Benz)o-phen. THF Ti(III)]Cl	(54.70) 54.68	(4.91) 4.39	(4.90) 4.91	(18.26) 17.90	dirty white	1.44	25.2	—	—	230°C (13.46) 13.40

* amount insufficient

Theoretical percentages are given in parentheses

THF = tetrahydrofuran; en = ethylene diamine; o-phen = orthophenylene diamine; dian = dianisidine; Benz = benzaldehyde; Bn = benzidine; MeO = methoxy.

and 1626(s) in these ligands and is in most cases shifted to higher frequency on complexation, i.e., 1651(s), 1650(s), 1645(s), 1650(s), 1650(m), 1620(s), 1639(s) and 1645(s) cm^{-1} respectively in the complexes arranged in the Table. In the complexes containing phenolic OH group there is no change in the i.r. spectra of the complexes in the region of OH deformation, that is 1200 cm^{-1} , and 1410–1310 cm^{-1} . Hence it is concluded that coordination occurs through nitrogen and not through phenolic hydroxyl groups.

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Thermodynamic Ionization Constant of Salicyloylhydrazide in Aqueous Solution

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MEAUREMENTS of the extent of ionization were previously made by the method of visual colorimetry by Hammett and coworkers¹ and also

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applied to spectrophotometry in the ultra violet region for cases where there was no visible change in colour². The present investigation involves determination of the thermodynamic ionization constant of salicyloylhydrazide in aqueous solution on which no data exist in the literature.

Salicyloylhydrazide readily gives coloured soluble and insoluble complexes with certain bivalent cations and thus is an useful reagent for colorimetric and gravimetric determination of the metal ions. The present investigation deals with the determination of the thermodynamic ionization constant pK_a . The data is of primary importance in various analytical procedures and in the elucidation of the structure of metal complexes.

Materials and Methods

Salicyloylhydrazide was synthesised³ and recrystallized from ethanol (m.p. 147°). Stock solution of the hydrazide was prepared by dissolving in ethanol and then diluting with water. All other reagents used were of analytical grade. All the solutions were prepared in conductivity water.

Optical measurements were made on DU-2 Beckman Spectrophotometer (Model 109200). Rectangular (1 cm long) cuvettes were used to take spectra; pH measurements were made on ELICO pH meter.

The samples for the absorption measurements were prepared by diluting aliquot volume of a stock solution of the hydrazide in water with a suitable volume of acid, alkali or buffer solution as required. The ionic strength was adjusted at 0.05M to 0.20M by mixing 1M solution on sodium perchlorate. The spectrum of each sample was measured from 230 to 345 nm.

The absorbance spectra of salicyloylhydrazide was determined in (a) 0.01 HCl, (b) a buffer containing glycine and NaOH of pH 8.6, 8.7 and 8.8, (c) 0.01 NaOH. The data obtained for pH 8.8 is represented in Fig. 1. The experimental results at constant ionic strength (0.10M) are given in Table 1

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of salicyloylhydrazide ($2 \times 10^{-3}M$) in aqueous medium at pH 8.8 A—0.01 HCl, B—glycine-NaOH buffer, C—0.01 NaOH.

TABLE I

Series	pH	Absorbance			pK _c
		Acid	Base	Buffer	
No. 1 (315 nm)	8.6	0.280	1.200	0.485	9.15
	8.7	0.280	1.200	0.520	9.15
	8.8	0.280	1.200	0.610	9.20
No. 2 (320 nm)	8.6	0.230	1.300	0.430	9.23
	8.7	0.230	1.300	0.490	9.19
	8.8	0.230	1.300	0.545	9.18
No. 3 (325 nm)	8.6	0.135	1.350	0.385	9.18
	8.7	0.135	1.350	0.425	9.20
	8.8	0.135	1.350	0.490	9.18
No. 4 (330 nm)	8.6	0.105	1.250	0.330	9.20
	8.7	0.105	1.250	0.375	9.20
	8.8	0.105	1.250	0.445	9.18
No. 5 (335 nm)	8.6	0.055	1.000	0.210	9.33
	8.7	0.055	1.000	0.280	9.25
	8.8	0.055	1.000	0.340	9.23
No. 6 (340 nm)	8.6	0.045	0.730	0.180	9.20
	8.7	0.045	0.730	0.230	9.17
	8.8	0.045	0.730	0.280	9.16
No. 7 (345 nm)	8.6	0.040	0.460	0.130	9.15
	8.7	0.040	0.460	0.160	9.09
	8.8	0.040	0.460	0.190	9.03
Average pK _c 9.18 ± 0.1					

Thus the average value of pK_c for ionic strength 0.05M, 0.10M, 0.15M and 0.20M comes out to be 9.57, 9.31, 9.0 and 8.65 respectively. The pK_c value extrapolated to zero ionic strength is 9.85.

The ionization constants at different ionic strengths pK_c were calculated at selected wave length from the equation

$$pK_c = pH + \log \frac{b-e}{e-a} \quad \dots (1)$$

where the pH is that of the buffer solution having absorbance "e", "a" and "b" are values of absorbance of same concentration of acid in 0.01 HCl, and 0.01N NaOH respectively. The value of the thermodynamic constant pK_a may be calculated with the equation⁴

$$pK_a = pK_c + \frac{I^{\frac{1}{2}}}{I + I^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \dots (2)$$

where I is ionic strength of the buffer solution. The average value of pK_a at 0.10M ionic strength has been calculated to be 9.88 ± 0.1 at a temperature 20°, from the spectra (in the region of wave length 315 nm to 345 nm). Further, the value of $-\Delta F^\circ$, as calculated from the above value of thermodynamic ionization constant according to Vant' Hoff's isotherm at 20° comes out to be 1.325 Kcal/mole.

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Spectrophotometric Studies on Complex Formation of Tantalum(V) with 7-Nitro-8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-Sulphonic Acid

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THE colour reaction between tantalum(V) and 7-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid has been studied to determine the optimum condition for analytical use of this reagent.

Absorption spectra and the effect of pH :

Absorption spectra of the reagent alone and solutions containing tantalum(V) and the reagent 7-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (NHQSA) at different pH values exhibit maximum absorbance at 375 nm. The results obtained show that the pH range for maximum and constant absorbance is 6 to 7.

Beer's law and stability :

The Beer's law is obeyed within the 1 mg. to 5 mg. of tantalum(V) permillilitre range.

The formation constant K of 1 : 2 complex calculated by Job's method and Mole ratio method¹⁻⁵ is recorded in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANT OF TA(V)-NHQSA COMPLEX

Method	Log K
1. Mole ratio	8.03
2. Job's	7.93
Average = 7.98	

Estimation of tantalum(V) :

Several estimations of tantalum were made by the method described above. The average of five determinations with 3.50 mg. of tantalum(V) is 3.45 mg. which varies between 3.43 mg. and 3.51 mg. with 95% confidence limit.

Effect of diverse ions :

Synthetic solutions containing 10 ppm. of tantalum (V) and varying amounts of diverse ions were prepared at pH 6.5 and tantalum determined in their presence. The following ions, with amounts in ppm given in parentheses, did not cause more than $\pm 3\%$ difference in absorbance.

NO₃⁻ (350), Cl⁻ (15), Br⁻ (10), I⁻ (15), Thiocyanate (250), Oxalate (125), Ba⁺² (105), Al⁺³ (10), Tartarate (300), Fluoride (350), Mo(VI) (450), V(V) (375), W (400), U(VI) (425), and Nb(V) (500).

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Condensation of Acetylacetone with Aldehydes

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AN attempt was made to condense acetylacetone with benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde, 5-bromo salicylaldehyde, *p*-hydroxy-benzaldehyde and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde. The main object of this investigation was to compare the reactivity of acetyl acetone with phenylacetic acid and its para halo substituted derivatives, in Knoevenagel's reaction. The condensation of phenylacetic acid and its *p*-chloro, *p*-bromo, *p*-iodo and *p*-fluoro derivatives has already been carried out in this laboratory¹⁻⁵. Another object of the investigation was to find out conditions in which maximum yields were obtained.

As the Knoevenagel's reaction involves carbanion addition to the carbonyl group of the aldehydes, any substance which yields a more stable carbanion will be more reactive. Phenylacetic acid as compared to acetylacetone is expected to give a more stable carbanion, because of the delocalisation of the negative charge over the benzene nucleus. Hence the yields obtained in the condensation of acetylacetone with different aldehydes should be lower than those obtained in the condensation of phenylacetic acid with the same aldehydes under similar conditions. This has been confirmed by comparing the yields obtained in the present investigation (Table 1) with those obtained in the condensation of phenylacetic acid with the same aldehydes^{2,3,6,7}.

Experimental

Condensation with benzaldehyde : Equimolecular amounts of acetylacetone and benzaldehyde were